
Genotoxic Impurities in Pharmaceutical Synthesis: Sources, Mechanism of Genotoxicity, Classification, Regulations, Chemical Classes and Analytical Methods

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Abstract Genotoxic impurities (GTIs) in pharmaceuticals at trace levels are of increasing concerns to both pharmaceutical industries and regulatory agencies due to their potentials for human carcinogenesis. Determination of these impurities at ppm levels requires highly sensitive analytical methodologies, which poses tremendous challenges on analytical communities in pharmaceutical R&D. Practical guidance with respect to the analytical determination of diverse classes of GTIs is currently lacking in the literature. This article provides an industrial perspective with regard to the analysis of various structural classes of GTIs that are commonly encountered during chemical development. The recent literatures will be reviewed, and several practical approaches for enhancing analyte detectability developed in recent years will be highlighted. As such, this article is organized into the following main sections: (1) Mechanism of Genotoxicity, (2) Classification of Genotoxic Impurities, (3) Acceptable Intakes of Genotoxic Impurities, (4) Chemical Classes of Common Genotoxic Impurities and (5) Analytical Methods.

Keywords Genotoxicity, Genotoxic Impurities, Pharmaceutical Synthesis, and Analytical Methods

1. Introduction

Most pharmaceutical products are manufactured either by applying a total synthesis approach or by modifying a naturally occurring product. In both cases, a wide range of reactive reagents are used. Therefore, it is natural that low levels of such

reagents or side products are present in the final active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) or drug product as impurities. Such impurities may have unwanted toxicities, including genotoxicity and carcinogenicity. The risk for patient's health caused by the presence of small molecules as impurities in APIs has become an increasing concern of pharmaceutical companies, regulatory authorities, patients, and doctors alike. Thus, pharmaceutical regulatory agencies such as the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) have raised concerns regarding the presence of genotoxic impurities (GTIs) in APIs that could impact negatively on human health.

There is an increasing scientific interest in this field, the importance of the field of genotoxicity, including chemistry, analytical methods, manufacturing, purification, diseases, medical aspects, genotoxicity tests, mechanism of action, assessment, and environment [1].

Experimental assessment of genotoxicity test models, such as the Ames test, allows direct study of genotoxicity, and the Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP) has defined GTIs as impurities that have been demonstrated to be genotoxic using such genotoxicity test models. The Ames test, developed in the early 1970s by Bruce N. Ames, is an experimental procedure to evaluate the potential carcinogenicity of chemicals, based on mutagenicity effects on *Salmonella typhimurium* histidine auxotrophic mutants strains. It became widely used due to its simplicity, low cost, and quick analysis without the need for animal testing. In the particular case of GTIs, “potential GTIs” are the ones that have structural alerts, i.e., functional chemical groups, for genotoxicity but have not been experimentally assessed; note that here potentially is not related with the presence or absence of the impurity [2].

In silico systems are commonly used to identify structural alerts and predict genotoxicity according to chemical structures. These systems follow either rule-based or quantitative structure–activity relationship models (QSAR). Rule-based systems are derived from identified mechanisms of action of chemicals in the cell genome or metabolic proteins. This approach was introduced by Miller and Miller in 1977 and followed by other authors [3]. In spite of its mechanistic clarity, it has been criticized as being based only on single interactions and therefore failing to be comprehensive. QSAR models may use several inputs simultaneously, e.g., information on Ames test results, log P, molecule polarity and electrical distribution, and chemical substructures. The use of QSAR models is particularly useful for the prediction of the biological effect of a broad range of chemicals and new molecules with a high degree of accuracy. This subject is further explored in several studies, and examples include comparison of the use of three models for prediction of Ames genotoxicity and presentation of different case studies [4,5]. QSAR models commonly used for determination of structural alerts to predict genotoxicity are the MULTICASE and the deductive estimation of risk from existing knowledge (DEREK) ones [6-8].

On the other hand, their presence in the manufacture of APIs is not stochastic, since these genotoxic chemicals often have specific inherent roles in the chemical routes used in API synthesis. The presence of such chemical in the reaction is a result of their introduction into the reaction in stoichiometric or catalytic amounts or as solvents, as well as their formation as side products (Figure 1). The presence of genotoxins is usually inherently controlled during API manufacture, as several stages of intermediate API isolation and purification are included in the production process, during which most of the GTIs are, together with other impurities, removed. Additionally, many of the synthetic reaction sequences initially designed for production of new drugs are often further improved through optimization of reaction conditions or by substituting with different reaction steps. Such improvements aim at higher yields, reaction selectivity, and more efficient use of reactants, which results in lower amounts of unreacted compounds and side products formed. Nevertheless, production of APIs with low GTI content is a major concern for API-manufacturing companies.

Figure 1: Sources of GTIs in API streams

2. Mechanism of Genotoxicity

Although it has now been several years since the introduction of the first EMA guideline on limits of genotoxic impurities, the terms genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, and mutagenicity are often misused by chemists. The term genotoxicity covers a wider range of genetic damage, regardless if such damage is or is not corrected through a cell DNA-repairing mechanism. A mutation represents a permanent change in the genome, which can lead to phenotype change, and a mutagen is a substance able to increase the frequency of such changes. A carcinogen is a substance that induces unregulated growth processes in cells, through damage to the genome or cell metabolic effects, eventually leading to cancer. In other words, mutagenicity refers to processes leading to genetic change, and carcinogenicity refers to processes resulting in tumor development, which may result from mutagenic processes [9, 10].

The mechanism of action of genotoxins involves an electrophilic attack on the nucleophilic center(s) of the DNA, these being nitrogen and oxygen atoms of pyrimidine and purine bases and the phosphodiester backbone, which could, in some circumstances, lead to strand breaks (Figure 2). Bidentate genotoxic agents can react with two nucleophilic sites, resulting in (i) one single molecule giving a bicyclic or tricyclic system; (ii) involvement of two different molecules in the same or the opposite DNA strand, affording inter- or intrastrand crosslinkages, respectively; or (iii) linking a protein and a DNA strand, giving a DNA-protein adduct [11]. Besides the chemical nature of the genotoxic agent, the stereospecificity of the reactions also depends on steric factors and nucleophilicity; for instance, the most nucleophilic sites of the DNA bases are endocyclic nitrogens, such as N3 and N7 of guanine and adenine, and on the contrary, exocyclic oxygens are less nucleophilic [9,12].

Figure 2: Attack on the DNA by genotoxins, where the arrows indicate the targeted nucleophilic sites of the DNA bases (based on Madeleine Price Ball's figure, GNU Free Documentation License)

3. Classification of Genotoxic Impurities

3.1. ICH M7, 2014 [13]

Compounds are classified according to their risk potential. ICH, M7 proposed a five class system for categorizing genotoxic impurities.

Class 1

Impurities known to be genotoxic (mutagenic) and carcinogenic. This group includes known animal carcinogens with reliable data for genotoxic mechanism, and human carcinogens. The genotoxic nature of the impurity is demonstrated using published data on the chemical structure.

Class 2

Impurities known to be genotoxic (mutagenic), but with unknown carcinogenic potential. This group includes impurities with demonstrated mutagenicity based on testing of the impurity in conventional genotoxicity tests.

Class 3

Impurities that have an alerting structure unrelated to the structure of the API, and of unknown genotoxic (mutagenic) potential. This group includes impurities with functional moieties that can be linked to genotoxicity based on structure. However, these moieties have not been tested as isolated compounds and are identified based on chemistry and using knowledge-based expert systems for structure activity relationships (SAR).

Class 4

Impurities with an alerting structure related to the API and impurities that contain an alerting functional moiety that is shared with the structure of the API.

Class 5

No alerting structure or indication of genotoxic potential. Compounds in class 5 yield negative result in structure alert assessment and hence no additional action beyond normal impurity monitoring is required. Compounds in class 3 and 4 which show positive results are further submitted for mutagenicity testing, with Ames and mini mutagenicity test.

Figure 3: Some examples of structurally alerting functional groups that are known to be involved in reactions with DNA (this list is not exhaustive)

3.2. PhRMA [14]

The Pharmaceutical Research and Manufacturing Association (PhRMA) derived a procedure for testing, classification, qualification and toxicological risk assessment of GTIs. It provided some structurally alerting functional groups (structural alerts or alerting structures) that are known to be involved in reactions with DNA. These were categorized into three groups (Figure 3).

Group 1: aromatic groups e.g. N-hydroxyaryls, N-acylatedaminoaryls, aza-aryl N-oxides, aminoaryls and alkylated aminoaryls, purines or pyrimidines, intercalators, PNAs or PNAHs.

Group 2: alkyl and aryl groups e.g. aldehydes, N-methylols, N-nitrosamines, nitro compounds, carbamates (urethanes), epoxides, aziridines, propiolactones, propiosultones, N or S mustards (beta haloethyl), hydrazines and azo compounds.

Group 3: hetero aromatic groups e.g. Michaelreactive acceptors, alkyl esters of phosphonates or sulphonates, haloalkenes, primary halides (alkyl and aryl-CH₂).

Figure 3: Potential Genotoxic Structures Characterization and Qualification.

3.3. International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) [15]

Group 1: Carcinogenic to humans.

Group 2A: Probably carcinogenic to humans.

Group 2B: Possibly carcinogenic to humans.

Group 3: Not classifiable as to its carcinogenicity to humans.

Group 4: Probably not carcinogenic to humans.

4. Acceptable Intakes of Genotoxic Impurities

4.1. Threshold of Toxicological (TTC) Concern-based Acceptable Intakes

A TTC-based acceptable intake of a mutagenic impurity of 1.5 µg per person per day is considered to be associated with a negligible risk (theoretical excess cancer risk of <1 in 100,000 over a lifetime of exposure) and can in general be used for most pharmaceuticals as a default to derive an acceptable limit for control. This approach would usually be used for mutagenic impurities present in pharmaceuticals for long term treatment (> 10 years) and where no carcinogenicity data are available (Classes 2 and 3 of ICH's Classification) [13].

4.2. Acceptable Intakes Based on Compound-Specific Risk Assessments

4.2.1. Mutagenic Impurities with Positive Carcinogenicity Data (Class 1 in Table 1)

Compound-specific risk assessments to derive acceptable intakes should be applied instead of the TTC-based acceptable intakes where sufficient carcinogenicity data exist. For a known mutagenic carcinogen, a compound-specific acceptable intake can be calculated based on carcinogenic potency and linear extrapolation as a default approach. Alternatively, other established risk assessment practices such as those used by international regulatory bodies may be applied either to calculate acceptable intakes or to use already existing values published by regulatory authorities. Compound-specific calculations for acceptable intakes can be applied case-by-case for impurities which are chemically similar to a known carcinogen compound class (class-specific acceptable intakes) provided that a rationale for chemical similarity and supporting data can be demonstrated [13].

4.2.2. Mutagenic Impurities with Evidence for a Practical Threshold

The existence of mechanisms leading to a dose response that is non-linear or has a practical threshold is increasingly recognized, not only for compounds that interact with non-DNA targets but also for DNA-reactive compounds, whose effects may be modulated by, for example, rapid detoxification before coming into contact with DNA, or by effective repair of induced damage. The acceptable intakes derived from compound-specific risk assessments can be adjusted for shorter duration of use in the same proportions and should be limited to not more than 0.5% or as in table 1, whichever is lower [13].

4.3. Acceptable Intakes in Relation to Less than Lifetime Exposure [13]

Table 1: Acceptable Intakes for an Individual Impurity.

Duration of treatment	≤1 month	>1-12 months	>1-12 years	>10 years- lifetime
Daily intake [µg/day]	120	20	10	1.5

4.4. Acceptable Intakes for Multiple Mutagenic Impurities

The TTC-based acceptable intakes should be applied to each individual impurity. When there are two Class 2 or Class 3 impurities, individual limits apply. When there are three or more Class 2 or Class 3 impurities specified on the drug substance specification, total mutagenic impurities should be limited as described in Table 2 for clinical development and marketed products. For combination products each active ingredient should be regulated separately [13].

Table 2: Acceptable Total Daily Intakes for Multiple Impurities

Duration of treatment	≤1 month	>1-12 months	>1-12 years	>10 years- lifetime
Daily intake [µg/day]	120	60	30	5

5. Chemical Classes of Common Genotoxic Impurities

5.1. Genotoxic Compounds Used as Reactants

Reactants used in chemical synthesis are usually selected due to their appropriate reactivity; however, this very same reactivity could result in genotoxicity. Often such reactants are not fully consumed, persist in the reaction mixture, and can be carried forward in the reaction sequence. Seven classes of reactants used in API synthesis were selected as examples to be presented in this section, including two types of alkylating agents, alkyl halides, and dialkyl sulfate; epoxides used in several addition reactions; hydrazine, a strongly reducing nitrogen base; TEMPO, a cyclic amine oxide radical; aromatic amines, used as building blocks; and boronic acids, used in carbon-carbon coupling reactions. Other well-known classes of potentially genotoxic impurities, aldehydes and aromatic nitro compounds, which are mainly used as starting materials and not reactants, are not included in this section.

5.1.1. Alkyl Halides

Methyl, ethyl, and propyl halides are used widely as industrial alkylating agents. Although the mechanism of their toxicity is still not fully understood, they have been shown to directly alkylate critical biologically active macromolecules, such as proteins and DNA [16]. The source of alkyl halide in APIs streams can be derived not only from direct use of alkyl halides but also from side reactions between alcoholic solvents and hydrogen halides or dequaternization of ammonium salts. It is worth mentioning that alkyl halides, such as methyl or ethyl chloride, deriving from low molecular weight alcohols, are volatile and readily purged from the API during the drying process. On the other hand, they can get trapped in the API crystal matrix and lead to trace impurities that are to be controlled [17]. The genotoxic alkyl halide impurities that used as reactants in APIs is summarized in Table 3 on the basis of the used halogen, reaction types, and examples of API synthesis.

Table 3: Some of Genotoxic Alkyl Halide Impurities that used as reactants in Drug Substances.

The Halogen	Application	API synthesis example	Reference
methyl iodide	C-alkylation	Fexofenadine, anastrozole	[18,19]
1,3-Dibromopropane	O-alkylation	Aliskiren	[20]
Methyl Iodide	S-alkylation	Lamifiban	[21]
4-chloro-1-bromobutane	N-alkylation	Aripiprazole	[22]
Methyl Iodide	Quaternization	Milameline	[23]
2-Iodopropane	Esterification	Latanoprost	[24]
2-Bromopropane	Cycloalkylation	Mazapertine,	[25]
Dihaloalkane	Cycloalkylation	Aripiprazole	[26]

5.1.2. Dialkyl Sulfates

The most common dialkyl sulfates used in the pharmaceutical industry are the methyl and ethyl derivatives, the latter having been used as a chemical weapon [27]. Being a strong methylating agent, dimethyl sulfate (DMS) (structure 4) is used to introduce a methyl group to atoms featuring unshared electron pairs, such as oxygen, nitrogen, carbon, sulfur, phosphorus, and some metals. Compared with the alkyl halide-type methylating agents, DMS is more

favorable due the higher reaction rate and lower possibility of byproduct formation [28]. Table 4 summarize the applications of dialkyl sulfate in API Manufacturing.

Figure 4: The structure of dimethyl Sulfates

Table 4: Applications of Dialkyl Sulfates during API Manufacturing.

Application	API synthesis example	Reference
O-alkylation	Rotigotine	[29]
S-alkylation	Rofecoxib	[30]
N-alkylation	Ralitoline	[31]
Aromatic alkylation	Telmisartan	[32]

5.1.3. Epoxides

Epoxides are the simplest cyclic ethers, featuring three ring atoms. Due to the large ring strain associated with the three-membered ring, epoxides are highly reactive molecules and thus are often used as reagents in API manufacturing. They easily participate in epoxide-ring-opening reactions with alcohols, amines, halides, organometallics, cyanides, sulfides, aromatic compounds, and active methylene groups. Table 5 summarize the applications of epoxides in API Manufacturing.

On the other hand, the high reactivity of these compounds makes them genotoxic, as their two electrophilic carbon atoms can react with the DNA nucleophilic centers, giving alkylated products [11].

Table 5: Applications of Epoxides during API Manufacturing.

Epoxide	Structure	API synthesis example	Reference
1,2-Epoxy-3-butene		Darunavir	[33]
(S)-2,3-Epoxypropanol		Rivaroxaban	[34]
Epichlorohydrin		Azelnidipine	[35]
GlycidolTosylate		Zosuquidar	[36]
GlycidolMesylate		Lubazodone	[37]

5.1.4. Hydrazines

The toxicity of hydrazine and its derivatives is ascribed to the generation of carbocations, carbon-centered radicals, and oxygen-centered radicals, which are considered to be highly reactive species. For these reactive intermediates, DNA alkylation and other DNA lesions have been reported [38]. Since hydrazine is a highly reactive base that acts as a reducing agent, it has been used as a synthetic reagent in production of several different types of drugs. Table 6 summarizes the application of hydrazine and some synthetic examples.

Table 6: Applications of Hydrazine in API Synthesis

Application	API synthesis example	Reference
Wolff–Kishner reduction*	Sunitinib	[39]
Hydrazide formation	Sitagliptin	[40]
Hydrazinolysis	Mofegiline	[41]
Electrophilic addition	Suritazole	[42]
Heterocyclizations	Sildenafil	[43]

*Wolff–Kishner reaction, where a carbonyl group(both ketone and aldehyde type) is transformed into a methylene or methylgroup through a hydrazone intermediate.

5.1.5. TEMPO

2,2,6,6-Tetramethylpiperidin-1-oxyl free radical (trade name TEMPO, Figure 5) is a commonly employed process reagent and potential process impurity. This compound was evaluated for genotoxic potential, and on the basis of the available, and somewhat conflicting, published data, it is considered to be genotoxic [44]. TEMPO is widely used throughout chemical- and biochemistry-related industries as a stable nitroxyl radical. TEMPO is mainly used for oxidations of alcohols to yield aldehydes and ketones or carboxylic acids [45].

Figure 5: The structure of TEMPO.

Some examples of use TEMPO in the API manufacturing are Darunavir [46], Maraviroc [47], Oseltamivir [48].

5.1.6. Aromatic Amines

Although aromatic amines are generally not inherently genotoxic, during metabolic activation, electrophilic species are generated. The main transformation pathway of aromatic amine metabolism is oxidation, producing an N-hydroxy compound that is conjugated as an acetate, sulfate, or glucuronide. Further deconjugation results in a nitrenium ion (ArN^+H), which is considered to be the active genotoxin that binds to DNA [49].

Aromatic amines are often present as starting material, intermediate, or reagent in pharmaceutical synthesis.

Table 7. Applications of Hydrazine in API Synthesis.

Aromatic Amines	API synthesis example	The function	Reference
4-dimethylaminopyridine	Mometasonefuroate	Catalyst	[50]
2,6-dichloroaniline	Diclofenac	Starting material	[51]
2,6-dimethylaniline	Lidocaine	Starting material	[52]
4-chloroaniline.	Chlorhexidine	Reactant	[53]

5.1.7. Boronic Acids

Boronic acids have been recently tested and identified as a novel family of bacterial mutagens. However, there is no direct evidence of direct covalent binding between them and DNA. Twelve out of the 13 boronic acid derivatives recently tested by O'Donovan et al. were shown to be mutagenic [54]. Boronic acids and their ester-type derivatives are important intermediates in synthetic organic chemistry because they are easy to handle and act as mild organic Lewis acids. They are also considered to be environmentally friendly, since they give boric acid as the side product during their application [55]. An example of the use of Boronic Acid derivatives in API synthesis: Garenoxacin [56], Losartan [57].

5.2. Genotoxic Compounds Formed in Side Reactions

Examples of the previous section refer to genotoxic impurities introduced as reactants; however, genotoxic impurities can be formed as side products during API synthesis. A class that has drawn the most attention and that has been the most extensively studied when compared to other GTI classes is the sulfonate esters. This class of molecules is usually formed in side reactions with alcohols, and therefore, awareness for their presence in API synthesis could be, initially, not so straight forward [58].

5.2.1. Sulfonate Esters

Sulfonate esters are alkylating agents, a class of potentially genotoxic compounds [59]. They are called alkylating agents due to their ability per se, or after metabolic activation, of adding alkyl residues to the reactive nucleophile sites of the DNA bases. They cover a wide range of chemical structures from the simplest alkyl sulfonates to more complex structures featuring aromatic systems with various functional groups.

Table : Common Sulfonate Ester Impurities and their Precursors.

GTI	GTI structure	GTI precursor
mesylates (methanesulfonate)	Me-SO ₃ Me	Me-SO ₃ H
triflates (trifluoromethanesulfonate)	F ₃ C-SO ₃ Me	F ₃ C-SO ₃ H F ₃ C-SO ₂ Cl
Tosylates (p-toluenesulfonate)		
nosylate (4-nitrobenzenesulfonate),		
mesylates (methanesulfonate)	Me-SO ₃ Me	Me-SO ₃ H

The use of such compounds in stoichiometric amounts include their function as/in (a) API salt forming agents, (b) good leaving groups, (c) cyclization agents, (d) protecting agents, (e) Mitsunobu rearrangement; (f) sulfonamide formation, and (g) aids for the resolution of isomers. Sulfonate esters and their precursors can be used in catalytic amounts also in (a) cyclizations, (b) protecting group manipulations, (c) double bond migration, (d) enamine-amine reduction, and (e) esterification.

5.2.2. Alkyl Halides

The source of alkyl halide in APIs streams can be derived not only from direct use of alkyl halides but also from side reactions between alcoholic solvents and hydrogen halides or dequaternization of ammonium salts.

This is illustrated by the recent use of 4-(4,6-dimethoxy-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)-4-methylmorpholinium chloride (DMTMM), Figure 6, which is an efficient coupling agent in a wide range of organic reactions [60,61], such as

esterification [62,63], glycosidation [64] and phosphorylation [65] in the synthesis of antibiotics [66], peptides [67], and alkaloids [68]. However, DMTMM is unstable in organic solvents and reacts with itself, yielding 4-(4,6-dimethoxy-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)-4-morpholine and genotoxic methyl chloride.

Figure 6: The structure of DMTMM

The sources for genotoxic alkyl halide impurities derived from side reactions in APIs is summarized in Table 9 on the basis of the source of the impurity, reaction types, and examples of API synthesis.

Table 9. genotoxic alkyl halide impurities derived from side reactions.

GTI source	GTI	Application	API synthesis example	Reference
Dequaternization	DMTMM	coupling reactions	Antibiotics, peptides, alkaloids	[66,67,68]
Use of hydrogen halides in alcoholic solvents	Hydrogen Chloride/ Methanol	Cyclization	sitagliptin	[69]
	Hydrogen Chloride / Ethanol	Decyclization	Xemilofiban	[70]
	Hydrogen Chloride/ Ethanol	Decarboxylation	Sunitinib	[71]

5.2.3. Acetamide

Acetamide (Figure 7) is a known carcinogen; thus, the awareness of its formation in API manufacturing is crucial [72]. Although acetamide is not a genotoxin, Acetamide is not commonly used directly in the synthesis of APIs, but its derivatives, such as 2- and N-bromoacetamide (Figure) or trifluoroacetamide (Figure 9), are often used as building blocks in drug synthesis. These derivatives initially contain acetamide as an impurity, but also the 2- and N-derivatives have potential to form acetamide, depending on the reaction conditions. Another source for formation of carcinogenic acetamide is the hydrolysis of the widely used solvent acetonitrile under acidic or basic conditions at elevated temperature. Acetonitrile is not only used as a solvent in the pharmaceutical industry but also as a reagent in API synthesis. For instance, it is directly used as a reagent in the synthesis [73] of corontin, which is a drug used for treatment of angina pectoris.

Figure 7: The structure of Acetamide

Figure 8. The structure of N-bromoacetamide

Figure 9.: The structure of trifluoroacetamide

5.3. Genotoxicity and Carcinogenicity of Common Organic Solvents

Organic solvents are ubiquitously present in pharmaceutical production processes as reaction and purification media (e.g., extraction), separation phases (e.g., chromatographic mobile phases), and also for cleaning of the equipment. The pharmaceutical industry consumes the largest amount of organic solvents in relation to the final product gained [74].

According to the Q3C guideline, solvents are divided into four groups [75]. Classes 1 and 2 are considered “toxic” solvents, as summarized in Table 10. The first group (class 1) contains known human carcinogens, compounds strongly suspected of being human carcinogens, and those presenting environmental hazards. These solvents should be avoided, unless strongly justified. The limits for class 1 solvents are listed as absolute parts per million in a material under testing (drug or excipient). Class 2 solvents presented in Table 10 ought to be limited, because they are nongenotoxic animal carcinogens or associated with irreversible toxicity, such as teratogenicity. Class 3 solvents, which include solvents such as ethanol and acetone, have permissible daily exposures of 50 mg, or up to 5000 ppm (0.5%) when it is assumed that 10 g is administered daily. There is no solvent recognized as being hazardous to human health at the average acceptable levels in pharmaceuticals in this group. They are less toxic in acute or short-term studies and have given negative results in genotoxicity studies. There is also an additional group, class 4 solvents. No toxicological data exists for this group, which would allow for the formulation of acceptable limits. When a manufacturer wishes to use class 4 solvents, a justification for the level of the solvent in the pharmaceutical product has to be submitted to the regulatory authorities [76].

Table 10: Classification of Common Solvents by the Q3C Guideline.

Class	Solvent	Concentration limit (ppm)
1	Benzene	2
	Carbon tetrachloride	4
	1,2-Dichloroethane Toxic	5
	1,1-Dichloroethene	8
	1,1,1-Trichloroethane	1500
2	Acetonitrile	410
	Chloroform	60
	Formamide	220
	Hexane	290
	Methanol	3000
	Cyclohexane	3880
	Pyridine	200
Toluene	890	

6. Analytical Methods

There are multiple challenges in the analytical determination of GTIs in pharmaceuticals at low ppm level. Firstly, there are diverse structural types, necessitating the selection and use of different analytical approaches. Secondly, many analytes are unstable or chemically reactive in nature, and thus requiring special handling techniques. Thirdly, an extremely high level of API concomitantly present with GTI analytes interferes with the analysis. Some low level impurities (known or unknown) may also interfere, especially upon exposure to reactive analytes [77,78].

6.1. Choosing the Suitable Separation Techniques

The first step of method development is to select the analytical instrumentation based on the molecular structure and in the context of the analytical testing limit [77,78].

6.1.1. Gas chromatography

GTIs can be generally divided into two groups based on their volatility, those that are volatile and those that are non-volatile. GC is the method of choice for analysis of many volatile small molecule GTIs [77].

Commonly used approaches include liquid injection and the headspace sampling technique. Liquid injection is prone to contamination. Injection of large amount of non-volatile API can accumulate in the injector liner or on the head of the GC column which can cause deterioration in method performance rather quickly (peak tailing, recovery, sensitivity, etc.). Headspace injection, on the other hand, is desirable because it minimizes potential contamination of the injector or column by avoiding the introduction of a large quantity of API. In this mode, the sample is dissolved in a high-boiling point solvent including water, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), N-methylpyrrolidone (NMP), or N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) in a closed headspace vial. Upon heating, volatile analytes partition into the vial headspace during an incubation period and the headspace vapor is sampled and injected into a gas chromatograph. The advantage of using headspace injection is that only volatile components, and the analytes of interest are injected, thus limiting the potential contamination of the injector or column. Non-volatile API does not partition into the headspace and therefore would not enter the GC system. Consequently, headspace injection becomes the preferred choice whenever possible. Nonetheless, many analytes that are amenable to GC analysis must be injected as solution because they may not have a sufficient vapor pressure to be introduced by conventional headspace injection, or may not be able to survive the high temperature incubation period [77,78].

6.1.2. Liquid chromatography

Non-volatile GTIs are generally analyzed by HPLC separation techniques, among which reversed phase (RP) HPLC is the most widely used separation mode. Many stationary phases are well established for chromatographic separation of various types of pharmaceutical starting materials, intermediates and APIs. Selection of columns and chromatographic conditions for analyzing GTIs should follow the same principle used in drug-related impurity chromatographic methods. However, because ppm levels of GTIs are in the matrix of an extremely high level of API, a good separation of the analyte peak from the main component is critically important irrespective of what detector is to be used [77,78].

Hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography (HILIC) is complementary to RP HPLC for the retention and separation of small molecule polar analytes and has gained increasing attention recently [79]. In HILIC, a polar stationary phase is used with an organic mobile phase such as ACN with a small amount of water (typically less than 30%, v/v). The small amount of water is believed to form a layer on the surface of the stationary phase, into which polar analytes can partition. Additional separation mechanisms such as ion exchange and hydrogen bonding are also possible and sometimes dominating [77,78]. Good retention can be achieved for very polar analytes that is not possible on RP HPLC columns. It is worth noting that the sample diluent must not be too aqueous, otherwise injection of high water content sample will result in poor retention of very polar analytes. Restriction on the use of water in the sample diluent could be a limitation on the use of this separation technique, especially when high water content is required for dissolving the drug substance or formulated drug product. The use of other separation techniques including normal phase HPLC, IC, CE, and SFC for GTI analysis appears to be sporadic and is not the subject of this discussion. The readers should refer to the relevant literature if there are specific interests [77,78].

6.2. Choosing the Suitable Detector

6.2.1. Detectors for GC

The flame-ionization detector (FID) remains the most versatile and widely available detector for GC. Its simplicity of use (equivalent to UV for HPLC) makes it the first choice for detecting volatile organic molecules. However, selectivity and sensitivity are somewhat limited for measuring trace levels of GTIs in the presence of large quantities

of API, and thus its performance is not always satisfactory. Because a significant number of GTIs contains halogens atoms (e.g. alkyl halide), electron capture detector (ECD) has emerged as an important detector in GTI analysis because of its unique selectivity toward to halogen elements. The sensitivity increases in the order of Cl, Br, I, such that alkyl chlorides give the weakest response. It is worth noting that the presence of other electron capturing species in the sample matrix could hamper the sensitivity or selectivity. Other element specific detectors, such as nitrogen-phosphorus detector (NPD), offer an additional tool for GTI analysis because of their selectivity and sensitivity, although wide utility has not yet been demonstrated. NPD responds selectively to organic compounds containing nitrogen and/or phosphorus. Another detector reported in the literature is the thermal energy analyzer (TEA), which has been used for the analysis of environmental toxins such as volatile nitrosamines [77, 78]. It is evident that mass spectrometry detectors including electron impact (EI) or chemical ionization (CI) operating in the SIM mode offer the most sensitive and selective detection in most GC methods. Because of its distinct advantage of mass selective detection (compound specific), an MS detector is much less prone to interferences compared to other methods. Due to the reduced background noise, MS detection in GC is the method of choice for trace analysis of GTIs [77, 78].

6.2.2. Detectors for HPLC

Several types of detection techniques are available for HPLC. UV detection is the most widely used detector in pharmaceutical analysis and most accessible detector in most laboratories. Therefore, it is the preferred choice whenever feasible. However, many GTIs either lack a UV chromophore or offer insufficient UV response at low ppm concentration. Furthermore, the fact that a UV detector is generally non-selective places more stringent requirements on the analytical separation. In certain cases, however, low ppm limit of quantitation (LOQ) methods are still possible as demonstrated by Yuabova et al [77,78].

Evaporative light scattering detectors (ELSD) can detect compounds that lack UV chromophores, however, this detector tends to be limited in sensitivity and dynamic range. The response is highly dependent on eluent composition and analyte volatility. Furthermore volatile compounds may get lost in the interface during solvent evaporation. The charged aerosol detectors (CAD) can also detect compounds that do not have a UV chromophore. CAD relies on the charging of the aerosol particles, which is in a way analogous to an atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) source in LC/MS. However, CAD is highly dependent on analyte volatility. Unsuccessful experiences in developing a method using ELSD and CAD detectors have been reported for investigational compounds and at the end an alternative MS method was implemented^(77,78). Chemiluminescent nitrogen detection (CLND) has also been explored for quantitation of low level pharmaceutical impurities since most pharmaceutical compounds contain nitrogen atoms [(79, 84], however, its use for analysis of GTIs has yet to be demonstrated.

In contrast, atmospheric pressure ionization mass spectrometry (MS), including electrospray (ESI) and atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) in single ion monitoring (SIM) or multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode, has been established as the most versatile, sensitive and selective analytical technique for trace analysis. Methods using MS detection have good precision and dynamic range. An accelerating number of publications report MS as the detector for trace level analysis of GTIs, either directly or coupled with derivatization approaches.

Recent advances in the instrumentation of ICP-MS have increased the detection sensitivity for some non-metal elements, such as S, Br, and Cl, which can be detected at ppb levels in solution. Carr et al. discussed the possibility of applying non-metal LC-ICP-MS to the determination of GTIs. Thus, it is reasonable to speculate that one could use LC-ICP-MS to analyze alkyl sulfonates and alkyl halides in the foreseeable future. Further improvements in the instrumentation may help achieve the detection limit required for GTI analysis [77,78].

6.3. General Approaches for Enhancing Detectability

Careful selection of the separation mode and detector is critically important but may not necessarily guarantee a satisfactory method. Additional considerations of the molecule's structure and properties to enhance detectability may be required in order to achieve the desired sensitivity. Several general approaches developed in the authors' laboratories are discussed below.

6.3.1. Chemical derivatization

A large number of GTIs are unstable or reactive and/or lack an appropriate structural moiety for sensitive detection at low ppm levels. Therefore, chemical derivatization becomes a general strategy that is useful in the following situations: (a) to stabilize reactive GTIs; and (b) to introduce a detection specific moiety for enhanced detection (chromophore for UV, basic nitrogen for MS, etc.). Of course, different analyte structures require specific types of derivatization approaches. General references on the selection of derivatization methods for analytical purposes are available in the literature [80]. The derivatization approach is sometimes non-specific, especially when dealing with alkylators. The reported derivatization methods for alkylators are not able to distinguish structurally related compounds [77, 78]. For example, both ethyl sulfonates and ethyl halides can react with a nucleophilic derivatization reagent, producing the same ethyl derivatives. On the flip side, such a derivatization approach could be advantageous in determining a group of structurally related compounds if the method is designed properly [77,78].

6.3.2. Matrix deactivation

Matrix deactivation is a chemical approach to stabilize unstable/reactive analytes during sample preparation and/or chromatographic analysis [77,78]. In contrast to conventional chemical derivatization where the analyte is chemically transformed into a stable and detectable species, the matrix deactivation approach chemically deactivates the reactive interfering species in the sample matrix. The matrix deactivation approach is based upon the hypothesis that the instability of certain GTIs at trace level is caused by the reaction between the analytes and reactive species in sample matrix. Thus, controlling the reactivity of the reactive species in the sample matrix would stabilize the unstable/reactive GTI analytes. As an example, electrophilic alkylators are destabilized by nucleophiles or bases via either nucleophilic substitution or elimination reactions. One way to suppress the reactivity of those nucleophiles and bases is to protonate the matrix, which is a very convenient and effective approach. A second approach is to add a nucleophile scavenger into the sample matrix to remove the nucleophiles completely. This is analogous to the use of an antioxidant and metal chelator to prevent oxidation in lipid analysis [77,78].

Another example of matrix deactivation is the method of M. Gricar et al [81], they addressed the matrix interference problem by dissolving the API in base and precipitating the free acid in acidic media; after filtration the supernatant was directly analyzed by HPLC (i.e. modified matrix precipitation). The optimal sensitivity was obtainable by using a low detection wavelengths, i.e. 205 nm and using a UV detection cell with a long path length, i.e. 60 mm. Detection levels for the azide impurity (LOD of 0.17 ppm and LOQ of 0.84 ppm) were significantly more sensitive than USP requirements, i.e. <10 ppm. The method was appropriately validated and gave good specificity for other common anions, good accuracy ($98.5 \pm 4.5\%$), linearity (LOQ e 101 ppm, R2 0.9999) and precision at the LOQ, i.e. RSD 3.9% [81].

7. Conclusions

Rapid development of extremely sensitive and robust analytical methodologies that can adequately monitor GTIs at very low levels is technically challenging. The biggest challenge lies in the need for high method sensitivity and selectivity, so that matrix interferences from APIs or excipients in the case of formulated drug products can be overcome. Although simplified separation and detection methodologies are desired in the manufacturing quality control laboratories, MS detection coupled with GC or HPLC plays a critical role in trace GTI analysis in various stages of pre-clinical and clinical drug development. This is primarily driven by the nonroutine requirement of method sensitivity, specificity, and speed of method development needed for project support. Analyst expertise in operating such equipment is a non-issue for organizations where specialized teams are responsible for GTI analyses. However, this could be a concern for some organizations where individual project analysts are responsible for performing such type of analysis for their own projects. It is not surprising, in those situations, that analysts are sometimes intimidated by mass spectrometry detectors and thus tend to limit themselves to the more common UV or FID methods. Although this makes sense from the instrument simplicity perspective, the analyst may need to struggle for the sensitivity and selectivity, and the method development may take an unnecessarily longer time. It is

our experience that the vast majority of the methods end up using MS detection because of the unparalleled specificity and sensitivity of this technique.

Understanding the molecular structure and properties of GTIs is the key to developing robust methods for their analysis. Being reactive in nature, many GTIs are unstable for direct analysis, so that low recovery and poor sensitivity presents a true challenge in trace analysis. In addition, some analytes do not have structural features that are amenable to common analytical detectors. Therefore, analytical strategies such as chemical derivatization and coordination ion spray-MS are invaluable tools for stabilizing analytes and/or enhancing their detectability. Furthermore, a "matrix deactivation" sample treatment strategy has been developed to effectively quench interfering factors in the sample matrices, caused by either API itself or low level impurities and solvents. This makes it possible to perform direct analysis of some unstable/reactive GTIs. Matrix deactivation represents a novel general strategy for stabilizing reactive GTIs and thus improving analytical sensitivity and recoveries simultaneously. By coupling these and other practical strategies with hyphenated mass spectrometry instrumentation, GTI analysis will experience a major leap forward over the next few years. Nevertheless, GTI analysis still represents a non-routine task, where method troubleshooting skills are highly demanding; it is our experience that a specialized expert group in analytical R&D can deliver the most efficient and reliable GTI analysis support to projects.

The challenges of transferring highly sensitive methods developed in R&D labs using the state-of-the-art instrumentation requiring highly trained specialists into manufacturing quality control labs should not be underestimated. Therefore, when a method is to be implemented in manufacturing labs, an effective GTI control strategy should be properly designed based upon process understanding. Simple HPLC/UV or GC/FID methods should be implemented by first intent whenever possible, while more sophisticated LC/MS or LC/MS/MS methods should be the last resort. Nevertheless, many manufacturing labs are now equipped with single quadrupole LC/MS and GC/MS instruments, and transfers of more methods that require these advanced instruments in the foreseeable future is expected.

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